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The Swiss Alphorn: Transformations of Form, Length and Modes of Playing

Knowledge of the development in length and form of the Swiss alphorn has until now been largely anecdotal and based on narrative accounts. The aim of the present article is to examine this subject by evaluating a comprehensive corpus of data derived from both historical artefacts and iconography. For this purpose, 37 instruments preserved in museums have been photographed and measured; this data has been supplemented with measurements from 20 additional instruments detailed in catalogues and museum databases. In addition, 285 paintings, lithographs, drawings and photographs of alphorns have been interpreted in their context of depicted surroundings. We have used this body of information in different ways: firstly, to trace the developments in length and form; secondly, to compare quantitative data with narrative accounts; and thirdly, to investigate the changing musical aesthetics of alphorn music based on the properties of historical instruments. The aim of this study is to provide a comprehensive overview of the transformations of the instrument, spanning the time period 1600 to 1950, by means of the largest corpus of data collected to date.¹ We have focused our research on this timeframe since pre-1600 sources are very scarce and after c1950 the alphorn in Switzerland has maintained its current form without significant alteration in terms of shape, length, or modes of playing. The data gained from the examination of images and

the measurement of instruments is described, and subsequently interpreted and compared with written information from literary sources. We consider the introduction and effects of mouthpieces, and evaluate documented developments with regards music-aesthetical motivations and impacts. With the number of instruments documented far too large to report specific details, this article employs detailed descriptions of exemplars for the purpose of explaining typical features and changing trends.

The alphorn is considered a Swiss national instrument and has been continuously promoted by the 'Federal Yodelling Association', a large folklore organisation of yodellers, alphorn players and flag throwers, since 1910. The Federal Yodelling Association (FYA) holds annual or biannual regional festivals, which include alphorn contests. Successful performers qualify to perform at triennial national festivals. The alphorn has a variant in the *büchel*, which, most popular in central Switzerland, is folded in the shape of a trumpet. Although usually shorter than the alphorn, the *büchel* is played in the same fashion and similarly employs only the notes of the harmonic series. Performances on alphorn or *büchel* at the festivals of the FYA include the playing of solos, as well as duos, trios, quartets or in larger groups. In other contexts, players may be accompanied by a symphony orchestra or church organ, and perform in pop, jazz, rock, funk, and experimental music that often focuses on the tonal aesthetic of the

¹ The funding of a three-year research project on the alphorn and its connection to yodelling by the Swiss National Science Foundation has made it possible to accumulate this large database of organological information.

harmonic series. Since the 1990s, there has been a growing interest in alphorn music in both popular culture and academic research; this reflects the fact that the number of active players is higher than ever before: estimates range from 2,000 to 5,000 players in Switzerland alone.²

As researchers in recent decades discovered the Swiss alphorn as a subject of enquiry from different perspectives, a small but significant body of literature has emerged on the topic and is briefly discussed here. Brigitte Bachmann-Geiser's research on Swiss folk instruments has resulted in a well-known publication that presents a detailed history of the alphorn in Switzerland, as well as many interesting facets of this instrument. Several experts contributed chapters on aspects of acoustics, learning and construction.³ Bachmann-Geiser describes major changes in the function of the alphorn that took place during the nineteenth century. According to Bachmann-Geiser, it changed from being a tool—used by herdsmen to call their cattle on mountain meadows—to an integral part of national culture, celebrated at folk festivals as a symbol of rural cultural heritage. Whether this functional shift correlates with changes in length and bore size will be discussed later. An investigation of alphorn music was undertaken by Hans-Jürg Sommer, who searched for an idiomatic, historical style of playing. Sommer analyses historical musical transcriptions attributable to the alphorn, proposing a distinct 'traditional' tripartite style of alphorn music: an 'invocation', a 'sequencing part' and a 'coda'.⁴ The performance of this 'traditional' music presupposes the availability of relatively large horns with a length of at least 2m. In her dissertation on the alphorn, Charlotte Vignau presents alphorn groups from Switzerland, the Allgäu (Germany), the

Netherlands and Japan, combining contemporary ethnomusicological aspects with audio-visual fieldwork techniques.⁵ The most recent dissertation on the alphorn by Frances Jones (2014) provides a detailed history of the alphorn's influence on Western art music.⁶

The origin of the alphorn's characteristic form remains unclear. Some folklore specialists suggest it derives from the form of a crooked fir tree grown on a slope, the original raw material from which the instrument was created.⁷ In contrast, the organologist Anthony Baines argues for a morphological adaptation from military trumpets. In his overview of the genealogy of brass instruments, Baines includes the alphorn in the context of different natural trumpets and horns: he describes physical properties such as bell shape,⁸ and notes similarities between the shape of alphorns and military trumpets in Medieval depictions of military horns, for example in Prudentius' *Psychomachia*.⁹ However, Baines also notes the substantial differences between military and pastoral music: "Their extraordinary freedom and variety [of the alphorn melodies] make the strongest contrast with the constrained formulae which marked old traditions of the military trumpet [...]. If in fact herdsmen copied some ancient trumpet they made free with the sounds, no doubt on the basis of the mountain cattle-call and yodel."¹⁰

Alphorn music was historically an oral tradition. The incorporation of alphorn players into the FYA since its founding in 1910 led to player-composers writing music for the instrument; before that time such notation as existed only occurred incidentally, as descriptive transcriptions and illustrations rather than prescriptive notation intended for performance. Like the music, the construction of the horns happened in informal ways, and the rare

² Brigitte Bachmann-Geiser, 'Die Mundart des Alphorns – eine DVD mit historischen Kühreihen', Schweizer Musikzeitung online, <https://www.musikzeitung.ch/de/rezensionen/tontraeger/2016/07_08/alphorn.html#.XIj1aNFCf1J>, consulted 11 March 2019.

³ Brigitte Bachmann-Geiser, *Das Alphorn: Vom Lock- zum Rockinstrument* (Bern: Haupt, 1999). Matthias Wetter contributed a chapter on the making of alphorns and büchels, Hans-Jürg Sommer on learning to play, and Res Margot on the role of echo effects in alphorn music. Rolphe Fehlmann wrote the chapter on the acoustics of the instrument.

⁴ Hans-Jürg Sommer, *Eine Auswertung und Interpretation historischer Quellen zur Alphornmelodik* (Oensingen: alphornmusik.ch, 2013), pp.33–35. 'Coda' was translated from Sommer's German term 'Zäsurteil' (literally: 'caesure part'), which he describes as interjected, slow passages (p.34).

⁵ Charlotte Vignau, *Modernity, Complex Societies, and the Alphorn* (Lanham: Lexington Books, 2013).

⁶ Frances Jones, 'The Alphorn in Western Art Music: A Cultural and Historical Study', PhD Thesis, University of Hull, 2014.

⁷ Brigitte Geiser, *Das Alphorn in der Schweiz* (Bern: Haupt, 1976), p.13.

⁸ Anthony Baines: *Brass Instruments. Their History and Development* (London: Faber & Faber, 1976).

⁹ Baines (1976), p.70.

¹⁰ Baines (1976), p.53.

accounts of alphorn making are descriptive rather than instructive in nature. For these reasons, the examination of preserved instruments, as well as an iconographical study, remains a promising method to illuminate the use, the sound and the musical style of the alphorn.

ORGANOLOGICAL PREMISES

As a wind instrument without holes or valves to adjust pitch, the alphorn is limited to the notes of the harmonic series. Partial 7, 11, 13 and 14 are regarded as ekmelic (non-equal-tempered) pitches: notes that deviate so strongly from equal temperament that they are perceived as ‘out of tune’ (Figure 1). In the revised Hornbostel-Sachs Classification of Musical Instruments, the alphorn is classified as an end-blown labrosone (423.121) with either straight (.1) or curved and folded (.2) tubes.¹¹ These can be played with or without mouthpieces. Nowadays, the alphorn is played with a wooden mouthpiece; the introduction and effect of the mouthpiece is discussed below.

Figure 1 shows the series of notes that can be produced on a modern-day alphorn. Harmonic 11 is colloquially called the ‘alphorn-fa’ and is considered one of the main characteristics of the instrument. On an equally-tempered scale with the fundamental note C, the ‘alphorn-fa’ is situated half way between the notes F and F sharp, at 551 cents above the note C, corresponding to a distance of 51 and 49 cents from the equal-tempered notes immediately below and above.¹² The distances to the nearest equal-tempered note in the case of harmonics 7 and 14 amounts to about one-sixth of a tone (31 cents), while for harmonic 13 the distance is one-fifth of a tone (40 cents). In performance, ekmelic notes play

a crucial role in moulding idiomatic alphorn tunes.

The number of different notes that can be generated on an alphorn is primarily determined by the length of the instrument. Modern alphorns with basic tunings in F sharp (length approximately 3.4m) or F (length approx. 3.6m) are nowadays the most common, and their repertoire usually uses notes ranging between harmonics 2 and 12. A higher range, up to harmonic 16, is largely the preserve of virtuosos due to the high level of technical performance skills required from players. Some of the historical forms of the alphorn tend to be shorter than their contemporary counterparts: as a consequence of this, the fundamental note and thus the entire playable harmonic series is located higher in the frequency spectrum and the critical, technically demanding frequency range is reached earlier.

Thus, the length constitutes an important feature of the alphorn as it determines the range of notes available to the player, and is relevant to the distinction between horns used exclusively for signalling and those made for musical purposes.¹³ Although the upper limit varies according to the individual technical ability of the player to produce high tessitura notes, it is necessary for the horn to be roughly 2m or longer in order to play as high as harmonic 11, the characteristic ‘alphorn-fa’.¹⁴ Unable to reproduce idiomatic alphorn music, significantly shorter horns were distinguished from alphorns and placed under the term ‘herdsman’s horn’ (*Hirtenhorn*) by Sommer.¹⁵ Because the distance between natural notes decreases progressively up the series, an increased length adds a substantial number of notes to the playable range. These factors demand the present comprehensive study of changes in instrument lengths.

Figure 1. Notes of the alphorn. Alphorn music is generally notated with C as the tonic, independent of the tuning of the instrument. Accidentals with arrows up or down designate ekmelic notes.

¹¹ MIMO Consortium: *Revision of the Hornbostel-Sachs Classification of Musical Instruments by the MIMO Consortium*, 2011, <<http://www.mimo-international.com/documents/Hornbostel%20Sachs.pdf>>, p.20, consulted 22 March 2019.

¹² The ‘alphorn-fa’ is not reserved to the alphorn, it appears on bagpipes, natural trumpets and a variety of other instruments.

¹³ Philip Drinker: ‘On the Construction of Alphorns: A Maker’s Experiences’, *Historic Brass Society Newsletter* 4 (1992), pp.22–26, at p.22.

¹⁴ Sommer (2013), p.13.

¹⁵ Sommer (2013), p.14.

Alphorn making in Switzerland became increasingly carried out by professionals in the twentieth century, so that by 1950, alphorns largely corresponded to the standard form favoured today. Vignau writes that since 1958, a designated 'Swiss form' can be spoken of: '1958 onward, it is known that the end-curved form could only be found in Switzerland [...]. A "Swiss form" seems justified at least from that time on.'¹⁶ For the most part, standardisation had to be completed by the 1970s when multi-part alphorn performances were given at folk festivals, for which it was necessary to have alphorns with the same tuning, and thus of the same length.¹⁷ Without group playing, there is no obvious incentive to adjust horns to the same tuning, as argued by Montagu in his study of the construction of *Midwinterhoorns*, Dutch relatives of the Swiss alphorn.¹⁸ The publication of the first instructive text on multi-part alphorn music by Johann Aregger appeared in 1971 and required the availability of alphorns similar enough to be played together in tune.¹⁹ The need for multiple instruments with the same tuning is nevertheless implied by earlier compositions. In the popular collection of 90 alphorn pieces published by Alfred Leonz Gassmann (1876–1962) in 1938, for instance, there are six duets and five trios.²⁰ Before 1900, few transcriptions exist that can be attributed to the alphorn and these are generally restricted to one part.²¹ In addition, these examples in most cases do not explicitly name the instrument and could be attributed differently, even to the singing voice. Albeit an isolated case, a source from 1815 suggests a duet of two alphorns tuned in F, played during festivities in honour of the Archduke Johann of Austria (1782–1859).²² In particular cases, alternative forms of the alphorn are still being made today, as instrument makers continue to experiment

with various forms and lengths. Information on the proportions of historical alphorns can be found in the form of anecdotal reports written down by travellers. These reports paint a diverse picture of variations, as summarised by Frances Jones:

There is documentation from many sources that demonstrate a variety of lengths and forms for an alphorn: descriptions of alphorns encountered by nineteenth-century visitors to Switzerland also report that instruments were between four and twelve feet in length [...]. The shape is also not standardised. Many alphorns are straight, while others have a gradual flare with no further bell expansion beyond that of the cone itself.²³

The few detailed records written prior to 1800 describe the alphorns in Switzerland as of varying length. One of the earliest accounts, including length measurements and exact descriptions of the design, was provided by Conrad Gesner (1516–1565): in his book on the mountain botany of Mount Pilatus, *De raris et admirandis herbis* (Zurich, 1555), he records that the 'alphorn' ('lituum alpinum') measures 11 feet in length (roughly 3–4m),²⁴ and describes it as 'cleverly tied with twigs' ('viminibus scite obligatum').²⁵ This description is unique and while important cannot be verified by other evidence. Perhaps more reliable is the work of Moritz Anton Kappeler, who in 1767 published an account of instruments he saw on Mount Pilatus, above Lucerne. In this volume, Kappeler gives measurements, describes how the instrument is made, its sound properties and the style of music that was played on it.

The alp-horn, as it is generally known, is a long tube made entirely of wood, the length varying between

¹⁶ Vignau (2013), p.11.

¹⁷ Vignau (2013), p.12.

¹⁸ Jeremy Montagu, 'The Construction of the Midwinterhoorn', *The Galpin Society Journal* 28 (1975), pp.71–80, at p.74.

¹⁹ Johann Aregger, *Das mehrstimmige Alphornblasen. Grundlagen & Kompositionen* (Engelberg: Johann Aregger, 1971).

²⁰ Alfred Leonz Gassmann, *Blast mir das Alphorn noch einmal! Was der Alphorner von seinem Naturinstrument wissen muss* (Zürich and Leipzig: Hug & Co., 1938), pp.50–51, 94–105.

²¹ Overviews of the manuscripts concerned are provided by Sommer (2013) and Ammann, Kammermann and Wey, *Alpenstimmung. Musikalische Beziehung zwischen Alphorn und Jodel – Fakt oder Ideologie?* (Zürich: Chronos, 2019).

²² Wolfgang Suppan, 'Das Basler Erzherzog-Johann-Fest von 1815', *Mitteilungen des Steirischen Tonkünstlerbundes* 82 (1982), pp.89–97, at p.96.

²³ Jones (2014), p.14.

²⁴ Conversion to metres according to Anne-Marie Dubler: 'Masse und Gewichte', *Historisches Lexikon der Schweiz* (HLS), 2011, <<http://www.hls-dhs-dss.ch/textes/d/D13751.php?topdf=1>>, p.3, consulted 17 May 2017. Dubler reports a large range of 26–36cm per foot.

²⁵ Conrad Gesner, *de raris et admirandis herbis, quae sive quod noctu luceant, sive alias ob causas, lunariae nominantur, commentariolus* (Zürich: Andreas and Jakob Gesner, 1555), p.52; translations from the Latin by the authors.

Figure 2. Number of alphorn depictions (vertical axis) per decade (horizontal axis) in our corpus, 1600–1950.

4 and 12 feet: the curve follows the exact shape of a geometric cissoidal curve: from the bottom opening of 3 to 5 fingers wide it gradually becomes narrower so that where the mouth is placed there is an opening of 1½ thumb widths, internally it is jointed, with long thin lengths, and for its whole length it is tightly bound together externally with flexible twigs: and so that there are no gaps to let air out it is covered all over with pitch and wax. It gives a very deep, penetrating sound, which though not too powerful close by, can be heard a long distance away [...].²⁶

Kappeler's detailed description points out the small bore of only '3 to 5 fingers' wide at the opening. Contrasting the exact measurement of the bore, he states that the length varied from '4 to 12 feet'. *The Historical Dictionary of Switzerland* recommends to assume a foot length of 26–36cm for this time period;²⁷ thus the statement of 4 feet corresponds to 104–144cm, and 12 feet corresponds to 312–432cm. As the quotes by Gesner and Kappeler are the only known specific and detailed sources from Switzerland before 1800, the phenomenology of the alphorn of those times remains generally unknown. It is also notable that both sources concern the same region, Mount Pilatus near the city of Lucerne.

ASSESSMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE LENGTH BASED ON THE PICTORIAL RECORD

As we have intimated, accounts of the length and form of the alphorn to date have remained anecdotal and based on narrative accounts. The aim of the present study is to reconsider this subject by evaluating a corpus of data consisting of paintings, lithographs, drawings and photographs. In order to accumulate data on the development of instrument lengths, 285 illustrations depicting alphorns have been collected. For the present study we have used the term 'alphorn' to mean wooden natural trumpets without valves or slides, whose cultural background lies in the Alpine region. The *büchel*, the curved and shorter variant of the alphorn, is included and labeled accordingly in this study. Natural trumpets of urban or military origin are not included. Figure 2 summarises the distribution of alphorn images per decade for the timespan 1600 to 1950.

A significant peak in the number of alphorn images occurs at the beginning of the nineteenth century (see Figure 2). Towards the middle of the nineteenth century, however, there is a decline in images, before a steady increase towards 1900. While the collection of works examined is likely to be biased towards older depictions, as these

²⁶ Moritz Anton Kappeler, *Pilati Montis Historia* (Lucerne, 1767); translation from the Latin quoted after Jones (2014), p.14. 'Cissoidal' refers to a specific geometrical curve in the shape of an alphorn.

²⁷ Dubler (2011), p.3.

Figure 3. *Development of the length of the alphorn based on paintings, drawings, lithographs and photographs. The overview shows the estimated lengths (in cm) of a total of 250 illustrations dating from the period c1600 to 1950. The lengths are based on independent estimates made by two people.*

are preserved and disseminated in literature as historical examples, nonetheless pre-eighteenth-century images are relatively scarce. In the twentieth century, photography gradually replaces other forms of iconography as the main medium of portrayal. Although the length of depicted instruments can only be estimated in comparison with other objects or people, that artistic freedom must be taken into account, and that the epoch-dominating idealisation in pictorial representations must not be ignored, nevertheless this iconographic approach remains a useful way to deduce the length of an instrument based on the proportions depicted. Figure 3 records dated representations in which the alphorn is situated in a pictorial context where persons or objects enable an estimate of the length of the instrument. Of the 285 images examined, 250 allowed us to estimate the length of the alphorn based on its environment, for example the depiction of a person holding the horn; 35 did not have enough contextual information and are excluded from this analysis. The estimates made by two independent assessors showed a close correlation.²⁸ Tables

detailing the sources of all pictures as well as the results are available online.²⁹

The relatively few alphorn images from the seventeenth century show relatively short instruments of 1.3–1.8m in length. This span remains largely unchanged throughout the eighteenth century, a time period that already provides more sources and hence a more reliable picture. As depictions increase, lengths show more variety, ranging from less than one metre to more than three. Observable in the right part of Figure 3, lengths drastically increase at the turn of the twentieth century. Thus, we suggest that the thrust towards a standardised form and length of the alphorn may be dated earlier than previously assumed, although without being consistent, as differing forms existed and were created in the same period during which the standardisation progressed. A similar attempt regarding standardisation may be postulated for the time period of folklore momentum in the early nineteenth century, although there are a number of exceptions. In the period concerned, the majority of alphorns detailed in the pictorial record measure between 1.5 and 2m, corresponding

²⁸ A two-way model intraclass correlation coefficient (icc) was calculated, showing a high consistency of 0.874 between the two assessors.

²⁹ The dataset is available on the Galpin Society website <<http://galpinsociety.org>>, under journal and then supplementary material.

Figure 4. *Nineteenth-century alphorn from Central Switzerland, preserved in the Collection of Musical Instruments Willisau (MSP 236).*

to a tuning between A₂ and E₂. The construction of the instruments of this length indicated the ability to perform melodies using the tonal range up to harmonic 12, thereby including the characteristic ‘alphorn-fa’.

The most informative result of the evaluation of the visual documentation is the growth in length occurring around 1900. Although smaller specimens are still depicted, the accumulation of horns larger than 2.5m is conspicuous. Towards the turn of the twentieth century, there are an increasing number of photographic images. Since the photographs are in many cases portraying old instruments, we have to allow for the possibility of a timelag between the date of the image and the date the alphorn was actually created. While the instruments at the beginning of the twentieth century still vary in length, shape and pitch, a large number towards the mid-twentieth century are increasingly similar to today’s standard. In addition, the pictorial records suggests that the mode of playing also underwent a physical change: illustrations from the sixteenth, seventeenth and eighteenth centuries predominantly show players blowing their horns whilst holding them straight in front of them; from the turn of the nineteenth century, performers tend to place the end of the instrument either on the ground or in the fork of a branch.

ORGANOLOGICAL TRENDS AND VARIATIONS BASED ON ALPHORNS IN MUSEUMS

In order to gain a comprehensive picture of historical alphorns, 37 instruments preserved in Swiss museums and private collections have been measured and photographed. Another 20 instruments had already been examined and their data was already

available.³⁰ For all the instruments we examined, we measured the overall length,³¹ the diameter of the bell and the inner diameter of the bore of the mouthpiece receiver. In cases where the bell was not circular but elliptical or irregularly shaped, we measured the extremes and state the mean value of the diameter. All of these measurements are given in Table 1.

A relatively small number of these instruments are in a state of preservation that still allows them to be played and one can thereby obtain an impression of their sound. One such instrument, located in the Collection of Musical Instruments Willisau (Canton of Lucerne), was examined in detail by the authors in 2016. The alphorn, depicted in Figure 4, measures 2.64m in length and comprises two tubes, each wrapped with fir roots and strips of willow, that are joined together at approximately the middle of the instrument. The conical bell is bent and has an opening of 13cm; the bore of the mouthpiece receiver measures 1.5cm.

In addition to data gathered from measurements, we gained further information on this alphorn from a document of 1909 written by the collector Heinrich Schumacher (1858–1923) that includes a report on how the instrument was made. According to Schumacher, the raw material was ‘first cut in half lengthwise, then hollowed out and glued together again and with roots of white fir, split in the middle, very tightly wound. A very boring and difficult task, since the roots are rarely straight.’³² The information that Schumacher provides gives a rare insight into the process by a witness from the time the instrument was placed in a collection.

Table 1 offers an overview of the instruments preserved in Swiss museums, as well as examples

³⁰ The location of museum instruments, as well as to alphorn makers, may be found in Bachmann-Geiser (1999), p.220; Walter Kälin: *Die Blasinstrumente in der Schweiz. Hersteller und Händler vom 16. Jahrhundert bis Ende des 20. Jahrhunderts* (Zürich: Eigenverlag der Gesellschaft der Freunde alter Musikinstrumente); and in the MIMO database: <<http://www.mimo-international.com/MIMO/accueil-ermes.aspx>>, consulted 27 March 2019.

³¹ Note that these measurements, carried out by placing a cord alongside the alphorn, can deviate by a few centimetres within consecutive measurements.

³² Heinrich Schumacher, ‘127. Alphorn’, unpublished manuscript, 1909. Transcription of the handwriting and translation from the German by the authors.

held in Leipzig, Edinburgh and Brussels. Abbreviations in the 'source' column refer to the following collections (if not indicated otherwise the data was collected by the authors): BHM: Bern Historical Museum;³³ BKJV: Bernese Cantonal Yodelling Association; DMZ: Zeihen Village Museum; KSB: Playing Collection of Historical Musical Instruments, Bern; MKB: Museum of Cultures Basel; MSW: Musical Instrument Collection Willisau; MIMEd: Musical Instrument Museums Edinburgh;³⁴ MMUL: Museum of Musical Instruments of the University of Leipzig;³⁵ MIB: Musical Instruments Museum, Brussels;³⁶ PHT: private property of Heinz Tschiemer; PKL: private property of Kurt Langhard; LM: National Museum

Zurich;³⁷ TCM: Thun Castle Museum; TML: Lauterbrunnen Valley Museum. The objects are ordered by date of construction. However, the dating of these artefacts has proved to be problematic: even though most instruments are dated in the inventories, the origin and the reliability of this information remains largely unclear. In some cases, the date of the instrument arriving in the collection is provided, therefore a date of 1900, for example, is to be read as 'not later than 1900'. In addition, some of the dates remain vague and only designate a certain century. Instruments with an asterisk in the 'mouthpiece' column do not feature a mouthpiece, but have a small cup-shape carved into the top of the leadpipe.³⁸

No.	Designation	Date	Length (cm)	Bell diameter (mean, cm)	Bore diameter (cm)	Mouthpiece	Origin	Source (inventory number)
1	Alphorn, <i>Signalhorn</i>	c1700	191	7.5	1.6	no	Canton of Uri	DMZ (no. 248)
2	Alphorn	c1700	158	13	1.5	-	Canton of Bern	TCM (no. 1162)
3	Alphorn, <i>Unspunnenhorn</i>	c1720	240	8.3	1.9	*	Canton of Bern	TCM (no. 1163)
4	Alphorn, <i>Krummholz</i>	c1750	174	11	2	no	Canton of Uri	DMZ (no. 3)
5	<i>Stockbüchel</i>	c1800	222	8.6	1.5	yes	Austria or Switzerland	MSW (RWM 148)
6	Alphorn, <i>Hirtenhorn</i>	c1800 (?)	115.5	7.5	-	*	Canton of Bern (?)	BHM (no. 17237)
7	Alphorn, <i>Hirtenhorn</i>	c1800 (?)	132	10.3	-	*	Canton of Bern (Bernese Highlands)	BHM (no. 17278)
8	Alphorn	c1800	272	-	-	-	Canton of Bern	LM (LM 8482)
9	<i>Büchel</i>	c1800	246	8.5	-	yes	Muotatal	DMZ (no. 249)
10	Alphorn, <i>Unspunnenhorn</i>	c1805–1810	223	6	1.7	no	Probably Canton of Bern	BKJV (no inventory number)
11	Alphorn, <i>Unspunnenhorn</i>	c1825	194	7.7	-	*	Canton of Bern	BHM (no. 33716)
12	Alphorn, <i>Unspunnenhorn</i>	c1825	237	7.7	-	*	Canton of Bern	BHM (no. 33715)

³³ Brigitte Bachmann-Geiser, *Europäische Musikinstrumente im Bernischen Historischen Museum. Die Sammlung als Spiegel bernischer Musikkultur* (Bern: Verlag Bernisches Historisches Museum, 2001), pp.234–238.

³⁴ <<https://collections.ed.ac.uk/mimed>>, consulted 27 March 2019.

³⁵ Herbert Heyde, *Hörner und Zinken. Musikinstrumenten-Museum Leipzig* (Leipzig: VEB Deutscher Verlag für Musik Leipzig, 1982), vol.5, pp.105–109; <www.mimo-international.com>, consulted 15 February 2019.

³⁶ <www.mimo-international.com>, consulted 15 February 2019.

³⁷ Personal communication, Bernard Schüle, 16 February 2017; Bachmann-Geiser (1999), p.222.

³⁸ 'Leadpipe' refers to the part of the alphorn where the mouthpiece, when used, would be inserted.

Table 1. Overview of historical Swiss alphorns preserved in museums and private collections.								
No.	Designation	Date	Length (cm)	Bell diameter (mean, cm)	Bore diameter (cm)	Mouthpiece	Origin	Source (inventory number)
13	Alphorn, <i>Hirtenhorn</i>	late 18th c. or first half 19th c.	97.7	5.3	1.1	no	Switzerland	MMUL (no. 1619)
14	Alphorn, <i>Hirtenhorn</i>	late 18th c. or first half 19th c.	83	5.1	1.1	no	Switzerland	MMUL (no. 1618)
15	Alphorn	before 1850	210 (254)	11.3	1.4	-	Canton of Lucerne	MMUL (no. 1622)
16	<i>Tiba</i>	before 1870	120	7.4	0.6	no	Engadin	MMUL (no. 1620)
17	<i>Büchel</i>	19th c.	290	6.5	1.5	no	Switzerland	MSW (RWM 147)
18	Alphorn	19th c.	264	13	1.5	yes	Central Switzerland	MSW (MSP 236)
19	Alphorn	19th c.	277	12.8	1.6	yes	Canton of Glarus (?)	PKL
20	<i>Büchel</i>	19th c.	220	-	-	-	-	LM (LM 1393)
21	Alphorn	19th c.	336.5	16.5	-	-	Canton of Bern	LM (LM 16465)
22	<i>Büchel</i>	c1870	220.5	7.6	1.5	no	Canton of Glarus	MMUL (no. 1625)
23	Alphorn	c1875	342.5	17	1.3	yes	Lauterbrunnen, Canton of Bern	MMUL (no. 1623)
24	Alphorn	c1875	469	16.2	1.6	yes	Lauterbrunnen, Canton of Bern	MMUL (no. 1624)
25	Alphorn	c1880	350	16	-	yes	Canton of Obwalden	DMZ (no. 247)
26	Alphorn	before 1893	244	11	-	-	Switzerland	MIB (no. 1144)
27	Alphorn	1880–1900	373	18.5	1.6	-	Mürren Canton of Bern	TML (no inventory number)
28	<i>Büchel</i>	1890–1900	217	9.5	-	yes	probably Canton of Schwyz	LM (LM 68892)
29	<i>Büchel</i>	late 19th c.	220	8	1.6	yes	Central Switzerland	MKB (no. VI 11530)
30	<i>Touta</i>	late 19th c.	178	7.7	1.7	no	Canton of Wallis	MKB (no. VI 11584)
31	Alphorn	before 1900	206	9.6	1.5	yes	Canton of Uri	MKB (no. VI 17317)
32	Alphorn	before 1900	309	18.5	-	-	Switzerland	MIB (no. 2011)
33	<i>Büchel</i>	c1900	230	6.8	1.4	yes	Canton of Schwyz	MKB (no. VI 7533)
34	<i>Büchel</i>	c1900 (?)	234	8.2	1.3	yes	Switzerland	KSB (no. 859)
35	<i>Büchel</i>	c1900	239	7.5	-	yes	Canton of Bern (?)	BHM (no. 5536)
36	<i>Büchel</i>	before 1909	243	8.5	1.5	yes	Switzerland	MKB (no. VI 2721)
37	<i>Büchel</i>	c1910	248	10.7	1.2	-	-	KSB (no. 722)
38	Alphorn	before 1918	192	12.9	1.3	no	Switzerland	MKB (no. VI 8239)
39	<i>Büchel</i>	early 20th c.	281	-	-	yes	Canton of Bern	BHM (no. 33660)
40	Alphorn A. Oberli	c1920	307	27	1.5	yes	Canton of Bern	PHT (no inventory number)
41	Alphorn	c1920	387	23.5	-	yes	Canton of Glarus	LM (LM 154896.1-4)
42	Alphorn	c1935	343	-	-	-	Canton of Bern	MIMEd (no. 3097)
43	<i>Büchel</i>	c1935	222	7.6	-	yes	Muotatal	MKB (no. VI 41507)

No.	Designation	Date	Length (cm)	Bell diameter (mean, cm)	Bore diameter (cm)	Mouthpiece	Origin	Source (inventory number)
44	<i>Büchel</i>	c1900–1950	240	7.5	1.7	yes	Muotatal	KSB (no. 1552)
45	<i>Büchel</i>	c1940	341	-	-	yes	Canton of Bern	BHM (no. 38885)
46	Alphorn	c1940	342	19.6	-	-	-	LM (LM 58818.1-2)
47	<i>Büchel</i>	before 1950	231	9.5	1.6	yes	Muotatal, Central Switzerland	MSW (no inventory number)
48	Alphorn	-	245	21	1.3	-	probably Central Switzerland	MSW (RWM 111)
49	Alphorn	-	286	18	1.5	-	probably Bönigen (Canton of Bern)	PHT (no inventory number)
50	Alphorn	-	344	11.3	2.1	-	-	TML (no inventory number)
51	<i>Büchel</i>	-	237	8	1.5	yes	Central Switzerland	MKB (no. VI 35970)
52	Alphorn	-	215	19.5	2.3	no	-	KSB (no. 767)
53	Alphorn	-	308	14.9	1.5	yes	-	KSB (no. 762)
54	Alphorn	-	293	16.8	1.3	yes	-	KSB (no. 763)
55	Alphorn	-	336	19.4	1.6	yes	Canton of Bern	KSB (no. 768)
56	Alphorn	-	289	15.7	1.6	yes	-	KSB (no. 770)
57	Alphorn, <i>Unspunnenhorn</i>	-	217.5	9.5	1.5	-	probably Canton of Bern	PHT (no inventory number)

The table includes alphorns and *büchels* presumed to date from 1700 to 1950. Their proportions—length, bell diameters and bores—will be examined more closely in the following paragraphs. Concerning the regions of origin, the primary distribution is around central Switzerland (Cantons of Lucerne, Uri, Schwyz, and Obwalden) and the Canton of Bern. Notably absent from the list are regions of northern Switzerland, the French-speaking west and the Canton of Ticino. Arguably, the activities of the Federal Yodelling Association from 1910 onwards played a decisive role in the countrywide dissemination of a previously region-based musical phenomenon. As discussed in the evaluation of the visual record, the conclusiveness of these artefacts is relative. The durability of large, more valuable instruments probably exceeds that of small, casual creations. Furthermore, craftsmanship constitutes an important factor for the long-term preservation of a horn, as wooden artefacts can be subject to decay and inferior products fall apart more easily. Alongside the names ‘alphorn’

and *büchel*, comparable objects carried labels such as *Hirtenhorn* (herdsmen’s horn), *Tiba*, an unbent variant from the Rhaetian alps, and *Touta*, presumably an onomatopoeic word for a long, straight horn. The term *Stockbüchel* is ambiguous: it may relate either to the unbent variant of the *büchel*, or to an instrument designed to be easily carried up a mountain (*Stock*).³⁹ The designation *Unspunnenhorn* refers to a certain design from the cultural context of the *Unspunnenfest*, a folklore festival, and will be examined in detail below.

The lengths of the measured alphorns vary from less than one metre to more than four, showing how diverse the process of construction was at a time when no standardised designs and norms existed. At the same time, we observe relatively small differences in the cases of folded *büchels*, which vary in length from 2 to 3m. This relative standardisation of the *büchel* can be explained by a number of factors: the shape of the *büchel* was arguably derived from that of period trumpets; the folding of the instrument requires a higher level of skilled craftsmanship,

³⁹ Ernst Heim, ‘Das Alphorn. Ein Wettblasen in Muotathal’, *Schweizer Musikzeitung und Sängerbblatt* 13–14 (1881), p.99–102, 107–108, at p.99.

and an exchange of design details between the makers seems possible. Furthermore, the majority of *büchels* documented in Table 1 are attributed to the late nineteenth or early twentieth century, while alphorns are broadly dispersed across the whole period, and the *büchels* are predominantly of central Swiss origin. Figure 5 shows the distribution of lengths, comparing 37 alphorns⁴⁰ to 18 *büchels* based on data from Table 1. The black bars indicate the median values. Half of all values are within the square boxes, the whiskers enclose the minimum and maximum values.

The shape and the diameter of the bell did not undergo a clear, directional development. Its size varied considerably among the straight alphorns, and was relatively normalised among the folded *büchels*, the bells of which have a diameter of 7–10cm. Alphorns have generally larger bells

measuring as much as 30cm in diameter. Figure 6 shows the distribution of bell diameters among 35 alphorns compared to 15 *büchels*⁴¹ based on data from Table 1.

The bore of the leadpipe remains remarkably similar across all periods and regions. Of the instruments measured, some were not constructed for the use of a mouthpiece. Comparing these to the ones suited for their use, we observed a larger range of bores. Instruments with mouthpieces, or appropriate for their use, had bores of approximately 1.5cm, with very little deviation. Since the bore of *büchels* does not vary from those of alphorns,⁴² the two types are not separated in Figure 7. The majority of the preserved specimens were either equipped with a mouthpiece or designed for the use of a mouthpiece. In some cases, instruments may have been altered to enable them to be played with

Figure 5. Length in cm of (straight) alphorns and (folded) *büchels* dating from before 1950, based on data from Table 1.

⁴⁰ The numbers include the instruments so named in Table 1.

⁴¹ The numbers include only those instruments with data on bell diameters.

⁴² Jeremy Montagu: *Horns and Trumpets of the World. An Illustrated Guide* (Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield 2014), p.84.

Figure 6. Bell diameters in cm of (straight) alphorns and (folded) büchels dating from before 1950, based on data from Table 1.

a mouthpiece. Figure 7 depicts the distribution of different bore diameters from the 18 instruments with and nine without mouthpieces.⁴³

Two specimens in Table 1 stand out for their unusual length and width: both have their origin attributed to Lauterbrunnen (Canton of Bern) and both are preserved in the Museum of Musical Instruments of the University of Leipzig (no. 1623 and no. 1624). The two alphorns have been dated c1875 and were measured precisely by Herbert Heyde, who found similarities in their construction. The bores of both alphorns are slightly conical over seven-eighths of their length; they are curved towards their lower end, with widely flaring bells with diameters of 17cm and 16.2cm respectively. The instruments feature an attached mouthpiece made of lead and are constructed from two hollowed wooden halves, probably of spruce. The longer of the two alphorns (no. 1624) measures 469cm and

is tuned to the fundamental C sharp (where a^1 is 440Hz); the shorter instrument (no. 1623) has a length of 343cm and is tuned to the fundamental note F sharp.⁴⁴ Both alphorns are densely wrapped with split willow branches. The binding completely covers the longer horn; the shorter one is bound with the exception of the conical bell. Considering the coincidental dating and origin, as well as the similar construction of the two alphorns, it is likely that they were made by the same person. If so, the question arises as to why the two instruments were produced in different lengths and tuned a perfect fourth apart (in C sharp and F sharp). Concerning the length, the shorter alphorn concurs with the size popular today, but the longer one presents an unprecedented and rarely replicated size. Interestingly, the unusually large size of alphorns by the end of the nineteenth century in Lauterbrunnen is supported by another specimen that is held in the Lauterbrunnen Valley

⁴³ Including instruments with data on both mouthpieces and bore diameters.

⁴⁴ Heyde (1982), p.108.

Figure 7. Diameter of the bore in cm, comparing instruments (alphorns and *büchels*) with mouthpieces (black) to those without (grey). The vertical axis indicates the number of instruments.

Museum, and measuring 373cm in length. The alphorns held in Lauterbrunnen and in Leipzig show similar material and design and could possibly be attributed to the same maker. The Lauterbrunnen Valley Museum gives the maker's name as 'Bohren', but no further information on this alphorn maker has been found. The emergence of large horns in the Canton of Bern is noteworthy, especially given that several decades prior to 1875, a very different type of alphorn was predominant in the same region, the so-called *Unspunnenhorn*.

ESTABLISHMENT OF THE *UNSPUNNENHORN* TYPE

Although exemplars of the nowadays iconic form of the alphorn, characterised by a straight, slightly conical tube and a curved bell, can be found throughout the period of investigation, during the nineteenth century there was no such standardisation, and the shape of alphorns

depended on individual factors such as the pieces of wood at hand. Nevertheless, typical variants of the instrument emerged and prevailed at specific times. The most common historical form of the alphorn, presumed to have been established c1800, is named *Unspunnenhorn* because of its attribution to alphorn competitions held during the festivals at Unspunnen (Canton of Bern) in 1805 and 1808. The horns of this type are characterised by a narrow bore and a steep curve towards the bell, which widens only slightly towards the opening end.

The proliferation of alphorn iconography in the early 1800s (Figure 2) deserves attention. In this period, the alphorn began to be noticed by intellectuals. In a letter to the Bern authorities, Bernese painter Franz Niklaus König (1765–1832) made proposals for promoting the alphorn and reviving musical activities in the countryside, which were to lead to the first alphorn courses in the village of Grindelwald in the Bernese mountains.

König complained about the 'gradual dying out' of the alphorn caused by an 'ever-increasing inertia of the Alpine dwellers', the 'lack of good instruments' and the 'decay of morals since the revolution'.⁴⁵ He proposed the following ideas to promote alphorn playing:

The first requirement is therefore the purchase of alphorns which should be provided free of charge. An alphorn maker can be found near Walkringen. Those who are going to provide the necessary instruction will learn to play these instruments. Most useful help with this would come from Mr. Huber of Hofwyl, who is currently studying the alphorn for precisely this purpose. When some good teachers emerge, they should set up small schools in convenient places in the region, where both instruction and instruments should be provided free of charge.⁴⁶

The 'Mr. Huber' in question was the St. Gallen-based composer and trumpet player, Ferdinand Fürchtegott Huber (1791–1863), who played a key role in the establishment of a musical literature blending together folk tunes with formulas of period art music. Around 1820 he taught the first alphorn course in the village of Grindelwald in the Bernese mountains.⁴⁷ The instrument maker located in Walkringen remains unnamed, but a description of

alphorns near Walkringen at that time is given by Johann Rudolf Wyss, who writes: 'The one that I was able to examine more closely [...] was 4 to 5 feet long, and consisted of a moderately thick fir trunk, curved on the lower part, which had been cut lengthwise and hollowed out, but then tied back with raffia and made airtight with wax raked in the joints'.⁴⁸ According to Wyss, Huber was critical of amateur makers and the lack of matching instruments:

The sound of the alphorn comes closest to that of a slightly muted trumpet; but it is sharper and more pointed, especially the high notes. Only, with the somewhat negligent construction of the instrument, it is difficult to find a few that go together.⁴⁹

The Bern Historical Museum holds two alphorns of the *Unspunnenhorn* type (BHM no. 33715 and BHM no. 33716) from Walkringen that are dated c1825. They come from the family collection of Mülinen and it is believed that they are two of the six alphorns that were played at the first alphorn course in Grindelwald.⁵⁰ One alphorn (BHM no. 33715) measures 237cm in length and, according to the museum, is tuned in C sharp. The shorter one (BHM no. 33716) measures 194cm,⁵¹ and according to the museum, the fundamental note of this alphorn could not be determined, although with

Figure 8. *Unspunnenhorn*, Thun Castle Museum, no. 1163, photo by the authors.

⁴⁵ Franz Niklaus König: *Vorschläge zur Aufmunterung des Alphorns, und Wiederbelebung des Gesangs auf dem Lande*, Manuscript, Burgerbibliothek of Bern: Ms.Mül. 577(9), [1808], paragraph 1; translation from the German by the authors.

⁴⁶ König ([1808]), paragraph 1; translation from the German by the authors.

⁴⁷ Andrea Kammermann, Yannick Wey and Raymond Ammann, 'Ferdinand Fürchtegott Huber, Initiator der Beziehung zwischen Alphornmusik und Jodel', *Schweizer Jahrbuch für Musikforschung* 36 (2016), pp.12–37, at p.18.

⁴⁸ Johann Rudolf Wyss, *Sammlung von Schweizer Kühreihen und Volksliedern* (Bern: J. J. Burgdorfer, 1818), p.XIV; Johann Rudolf Wyss, *Reise in das Berner Oberland* (Bern: J.J. Burgdofer, 1817), p.892, translation from the German by the authors.

⁴⁹ Johann Rudolf Wyss, *Texte zu der Sammlung von Schweizer-Kühreihen und Volksliedern. Vierte, viel vermehrte und verbesserte* (Ausgabe, Bern: J. J. Burgdorfer, 1826), p.XII, translation from the German by the authors.

⁵⁰ Bachmann-Geiser (2001), p.236.

⁵¹ Bachmann-Geiser (2001), p.236.

this length of instrument, it should approximate to the note E. Whether the instruments held in Bern are in fact those *Unspunnenhorns* commissioned in Walkringen, and whether they were played at the festivals of *Unspunnen* in 1805 and 1808 remains unclear, as their dating and place of origin cannot be confirmed. In the search for original alphorns made in the early nineteenth century, another thread leads to Russia. Szadrowsky mentioned in 1868 that two grandsons of General Suvorov, who stayed in Hofwil, took two alphorns away with them. Bachmann-Geiser mentions the location of these in St Petersburg's *Kunstkamera*,⁵² but this assertion was denied when the curator was asked.⁵³ Visits and exchanges between the authors and representatives of several St Petersburg museums⁵⁴ did not lead to any concrete clues regarding the Szadrowsky/Bachmann-Geiser hypothesis.

In search of more alphorns of the same type, three more exemplars in the shape of the *Unspunnenhorn* have been found in Switzerland. One of them is in the Thun Castle Museum, a second is owned by the alphorn maker Heinz Tschiemer, and a third belongs to the Bernese Cantonal Yodelling Association.

Figure 8 shows the *Unspunnenhorn* held in the collection of the Thun Castle Museum. The instrument measures 240cm, the bell has a diameter of 8.3cm, and the bore of the leadpipe 1.9cm. When it was accessioned to Thun Castle Museum c1900, the alphorn was dated 1720, but a comparison with similar instruments and images would suggest a date of c1820. It is crafted with attention to detail, including the painting of the binding, which suggests a representative function, possibly for the attraction of tourists. Considering how popular this shape is in Romantic iconography, a possible case of 'reality imitating art' has to be taken into consideration. The aesthetic ideal of herdsmen playing this kind of alphorn could have inspired artisans to craft artefacts in this image. With regards the *Unspunnenhorn* we documented in the workshop of Tschiemer in Lauterbrunnen, Canton of Bern, it closely resembles the specimen shown in Figure 8 (length: 218cm, diameter of the bell:

9.5cm, bore: 1.5cm), but unlike the others it can be disassembled into three parts, a technique unfamiliar among nineteenth-century alphorns. Consequently, this particular instrument could also be an imitation of the *Unspunnenhorn* type, though of a later date. Another especially well-crafted and conserved *Unspunnenhorn* is the property of the Bernese Cantonal Yodel Federation, and has been displayed and played on several occasions over recent years. Thanks to the generous collaboration of Albert Feuz, we were able to examine this instrument, which is believed to date from the early nineteenth century, in detail. It measures 223cm in length, with a bell diameter of 6cm and a bore of 1.7cm. The firmly attached mouthpiece was not originally part of the instrument. Earlier, a small cup was carved into the wood; later on, the horn was re-modelled and a modern mouthpiece added.⁵⁵

In summary, the *Unspunnenhorn* type is defined by a length of 1.8 to 2.5m, a small bore and just a slight enlargement towards the bell which takes the form of a steep curve upwards. Although *Unspunnenhorns* are depicted in the nineteenth century, the age of the few preserved specimens remains unclear. Age determination by means of dendrochronology cannot be carried out because either too few annual rings are present or these are not clearly visible.

ALPHORN MAKERS AND THE TREND TOWARDS STANDARDISATION

The measurements of historical instruments can be complemented by and compared with literary sources of the relevant period. In an article of 1881, the musician Ernst Heim names the carpenter Alois Marti (1854–1925) of Hergiswil as a maker of alphorns. Heim noted the poor quality of the horns at a folklore festival and urged the Zurich section of the Swiss Alpine Club (SAC) to approve a loan of 300 francs to have eight alphorns made by Alois Marti.⁵⁶ According to Heim, Marti improved the process of making instruments and achieved better results: 'Through many attempts Alois Marti came up with the idea of making the binding from

⁵² Bachmann-Geiser (1999), p.49.

⁵³ Personal communication, Alexander Novik, 11 May 2017.

⁵⁴ Visits and/or inquiries included the Ethnographic Museum, the *Kunstkamera*, the Museum of Musical Instruments at Sheremetev Palace, and the Suvorov Museum. We strongly encourage further investigation by Russian researchers into the whereabouts of historical Swiss alphorns.

⁵⁵ Personal communication, Albert Feuz, 10 April 2017.

⁵⁶ Heim (1881), p.100.

fairly thick shavings of old, flexible walnut wood in the form of long, narrow ribbons. This cladding of the tube surpasses all other wraps in durability and beauty.⁵⁷ The varying forms with which Marti experimented were published as drawings by Heim (see Figure 9).⁵⁸ According to Heim's description, the instruments labelled 'No. 1', 'No. 2' and 'No. 3' produced the same timbre and were tuned to the same fundamental note. The first of these, a *büchel*, was constructed with the intention of creating a horn that is easier to transport.⁵⁹ In his experimental designs, Marti also suffered some setbacks: Heim states that the other three depicted, numbers 4, 5 and 6, were attempts to find new forms of *büchels* but had 'led to bad results.'⁶⁰ In the aftermath, the horns were distributed among herdsmen willing to learn to play in a contest. Satisfied with the outcome, Heim reported that

After everyone had played three times, as a finale there was a successful attempt to play the seven horns all together. After a short consultation the judges opened their verdict by saying that all seven players would receive the horn they played as a gift [...].⁶¹

That a 'successful attempt' was made to play the seven horns together suggests that Marti's horns were of matching length and pitch. As such, this source appears to be the earliest account of standardisation in alphorn making. However, it is an isolated case, since there were a wide variety of tunings in the 1880s (Table 1). Marti can therefore be regarded as a pioneer of innovative alphorn making and the first to successfully tune several horns the same.

Besides Marti, three alphorn makers may have contributed to the trend towards standardisation: Gottlieb Steck (1831–1895) of Unterseen, Canton of Bern, Josef Felder (1839–1918) of Schüpfheim, Canton of Lucerne, and Adolf Oberli (1879–1972) of Diemtigen, Canton of Bern. Felder collaborated with Marti to present alphorns at a national exhibition in Zurich in 1883, and it is possible that these makers exchanged templates of well-made

horns. The transition from individual construction to standardisation is mirrored in newspaper advertisements of the period, including from 1901: 'The instrument that was played at the alpine festival by Mr. Marti's son [Alfred, the son of Alois Marti] sold for 20 francs. Not to be missed in any mountain restaurant!'⁶² The advertisement thus emphasises the continuing construction of multiple alphorns after the successful examples from Marti's workshop. Furthermore, the reference to mountain restaurants as probable clients for alphorn makers demonstrates the economic connection between instrument making and tourism. The specimens described in Table 1 are made by anonymous instrument makers except numbers 40 and 55 which are clearly attributed to Adolf Oberli because this alphorn maker put his name on his work. Both these examples can therefore be regarded as prototypes of the forms dominant throughout the second half of the twentieth century as well as the twenty-first century up to the present. Some of Oberli's horns—one of them is on display in the Playing Collection of Historical Musical Instruments in Bern—are already almost indistinguishable from alphorns produced today. According to Heinz Tschiemer, Oberli is likely to have passed his designs on to two alphorn makers of the next generation, Ernst Schüpbach and Johann Kropf, who popularised this specific shape and contributed to a standardisation of design.

USE OF MOUTHPIECES

The use of mouthpieces facilitates the production of different notes and was presumably introduced and used by a number of performers in the early nineteenth century. Since the mouthpieces are similar to those of brass instruments, a transfer by brass players can be assumed. The influential proponent of the alphorn mentioned earlier, composer Ferdinand Fürchtegott Huber, was himself a trained trumpet player and talked about the use of mouthpieces. Before this introduction, or as an alternative to the use of mouthpieces, a cup-shape was carved into the leadpipe in some instances to

⁵⁷ Heim (1881), p.107, translation from the German by the authors.

⁵⁸ Heim (1881), p.99.

⁵⁹ Heim (1881), p.99–100. Smaller horns that were easier to carry may have been more in demand partly due to the development of the railway system and their suitability for easier transportation.

⁶⁰ Heim (1881), p.100, translation from the German by the authors.

⁶¹ Heim (1881), p.108, translation from the German by the authors.

⁶² Haas, Jakob, 'Alphorn!' *Appenzeller Volksfreund. Innerrhoder Zeitung* 56 (13 July 1901), quoted after Johann Manser, *Heemtklang us Innerrhode* (Appenzell: Genossenschafts-Buchdruckerei, 1980), p.202, translation from the German by the authors.

Figure 9. Varying forms of alphorns (nos. 2, 3 and 6) and büchels (nos. 1, 4 and 5) made by Alois Marti, published by Heim.

facilitate sound production. The specimen detailed in Figure 8 has a small cup carved into the wood at the upper end of the leadpipe. This method was documented in numerous cases, especially with the *Unspunnenhorns* described above. In 1826, Johann Rudolf Wyss published a quote from Huber where he talks about his application of trumpet mouthpieces:

After several attempts, which I made with such mouthpieces as are needed with trumpets, I found that with them, one can make the sound of the alphorn more round, full, and thereby agreeable; more comfortable especially for one who listens to it nearby. But, of course, the sound does not remain quite as natural as is inherent in the herdsman's alphorn without a mouthpiece.⁶³

The introduction of mouthpieces posed a clear improvement to the possibilities of the instrument, facilitating the production of notes and enhancing the sound quality. At the same time, it causes a compromise between these factors and the perceived authenticity, a loss of 'natural' qualities. Herdsmen continued to play alphorns without mouthpieces, and the method of hollowing out the leadpipe observed in various instruments described above can be attributed to them. The trumpet mouthpiece in question would have been made of metal, which should be taken into consideration in discussing the 'traditional' way of playing. Today, Swiss alphorn players mainly use wooden mouthpieces, while in the neighbouring countries, some Bavarian and Austrian players prefer those made of metal. The Federal Yodelling Association demands that performances at alphorn competitions be carried out with wooden mouthpieces, thereby aiming to preserve the difference in the sound from that of brass instruments.⁶⁴

MUSIC-AESTHETICAL IMPLICATIONS

The data drawn from the measurements above allude

to a number of aesthetic implications for alphorn music of different historical periods. During the seventeenth, eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, instruments typically measured 1.5 to 2m in length, enabling the player to produce up to 12 different notes. This refutes the hypothesis that the alphorn functioned exclusively as a signalling instrument at this time. The assumption, which can be found in folklore literature of the past century,⁶⁵ imagines the use of wooden horns in the Alps as primarily or exclusively for sending signals of alarm or calling cattle. Notably, the use of animal horns for signalling can be documented in the same regions.⁶⁶ Sommer assumes that signals played a role in the genealogy of alphorn music, but only as a part of the broader aesthetic picture.⁶⁷ This recognition implies that some transcriptions of so-called *Kuhreihen*, pastoral melodies emerging in the eighteenth century, could have been performed on alphorns of that period.

The overview of the visual record indicates the establishment of larger forms of the alphorn at the beginning of the twentieth century. This development was probably driven by a search for more acoustic precision. In his investigation of the acoustics of a modern alphorn, Rolphe Fehlmann concluded that the shape of the bell improves the intonation of the horn by correcting inharmonicity.⁶⁸ Therefore, the adjustment of construction towards the ideal of the harmonic series poses a reasonable justification for the tendency to standardise the form of the bell. A recent study shows furthermore that there are considerable differences in the accuracy of intonation between historical (pre-1950) and modern (post-1950) instruments.⁶⁹ The intonation of modern, standardised alphorns largely corresponds to the ideal of the harmonic series: the deviations are to a large extent imperceptible. The 'alphorn-fa' can be recognised as such and is unlikely to be confused with an equal-tempered note, since the mean deviation from the harmonic series (14 cents) is smaller than the deviation from the adjacent equal-

⁶³ Wyss (1826), p.XII, translation from the German by the authors.

⁶⁴ Eidgenössischer Jodlverband (ed.), *Technisches Regulativ für das Alphorn- und Büchelblasen*, 2018, <http://www.jodlverband.ch/images/alphornblasen/TechnischesRegulativ2018AB_D.pdf>, p.4, consulted 7 February 2019.

⁶⁵ Karl Klier, 'Etwas vom Alphorn', *Der Bergsteiger* 8 (1937), pp.526–533, at p.526.

⁶⁶ Eckhard Böhringer, *Tuba pastoritia: das Hirtenhorn und seine Verwendung in der Musik* (Balingen: Verlag des Schwäbisches Albvereins, 2015), p.168.

⁶⁷ Hans-Jürg Sommer, *Das Alphorn – Ein Signalinstrument?* <https://www.alphornmusik.ch/downloads/signalinstrument_web.pdf>, p.7, consulted 28 February 2019.

⁶⁸ Rolphe Fehlmann, 'Computer Simulations and Application of Numerical Techniques for Acoustic Waves in Curved Swiss Horn', PhD Thesis, Norwegian Institute of Technology, 1994, p.129.

⁶⁹ Raymond Ammann, Andrea Kammermann and Yannick Wey, *Alpenstimmung* (Zürich: Chronos, 2019). The study involves acoustical analysis of the tunings of nine historical alphorns compared to a group of five modern examples.

tempered notes (49 or 51 cents). In the lower octave, historical alphorns deviate from the harmonic series, which can be explained primarily by the individual construction method. Acoustic aesthetics thereby explain the shift towards larger bells and the shape of their curve. It remains to be noted that this explanation is contested by the nineteenth-century writer Szadowsky, who does not place musical but rather visual aesthetics as the motivation behind the development of the form. He sees large-bell alphorns as 'showpieces' for tourists, possibly alluding to large exemplars like those from Lauterbrunnen described above.⁷⁰ Recently, Vignau took up this hypothesis writing that alphorns were modeled according to their appeal to tourists.⁷¹ The two explanations are not mutually exclusive.

One of the hypotheses proposed in the introduction states that the central advantage of standardised alphorns with matching tuning lies in the ability to perform multi-part music in a shared tonality. Therefore, the introduction of multi-part performance at the competitions of the Federal Yodelling Association relied on the earlier developments in construction and was only incorporated in the 1970s. In 1972, the first festival to include multi-part performances with groups of up to four players was held in Lucerne. The reaction of audiences was enthusiastic. The chairman of the Central Swiss alphorn players, Fasi Kohler, wrote in a letter to the president of the Yodelling Association of Central Switzerland, praising the innovation: 'The first event of the Jubilee Yodeller Festival of the ZSVJ 1972 in Lucerne was not only a musical, but also a great public success. I remember the three or four listeners at the solo recitals and the massive audiences at the multi-part performances.'⁷² He then urged for the adoption of multi-part playing at future events. On 20 January 1973, representatives of different yodelling associations gathered for a meeting in Lucerne to discuss rules and modes of evaluation for multi-part alphorn contests.⁷³

CONCLUSIONS

In this survey, we have discussed the outcome of the analysis of iconography and artefacts, and

juxtaposed anecdotal evidence and historical sources of different types. This 'multi-media' approach to the alphorn at least partially succeeds in overcoming the problem of sources in a mostly oral tradition. At the same time, some discrepancies arise between different sources of data, for example Heim's account of alphorns of the same length compared to the wide spectrum found among preserved instruments of the same period. The data presented in this article mainly concurs with existing hypotheses stated in both recent and older literature, although some assumptions have to be scrutinised, and some dates adjusted.

The rise to popularity of the alphorn around 1800 is illustrated by a sudden peak in the occurrence of the instrument in the visual record. At the same time, the *Unspunnenhorn* type became crystallised. This type is characterised by a comparatively narrow design and a length of 1.8–2.5m. Whether pictures imitated objects, or the craftwork copied idealised depictions of Romantic-era artists, remains subject to speculation, as the few preserved horns cannot be exactly dated beyond doubt.

By estimating the lengths of alphorns depicted in historical iconography, an increase in length can be observed over time, particularly at the turn of the twentieth century. In addition, measurements of instruments preserved in museums shed light on the development in the craft of alphorn making. The standardisation of length and form, resulting in alphorns of around 3.4 metres, with large, curved bells, arguably started towards the end of the nineteenth century and was probably driven by the innovations and collaborations between the foremost alphorn makers, namely Marti, Steck, Felder, Oberli, Schüpbach and Kropf. Until 1900, the alphorns vary substantially in terms of length, and therefore in tuning. The form of the *büchel*, folded in the shape of a trumpet, shows less variations, which is reflected by how little the bell diameters and the bores deviate among surviving instruments. The measurement of the bore indicates that the use of mouthpieces was widespread, and therefore the bore was adjusted to accommodate these tools for playing.

⁷⁰ Heinrich Szadowsky, 'Die Musik und die tonerzeugenden Instrumente der Alpenbewohner', *Jahrbuch des Schweizer Alpenclubs* 4 (1867/68), pp.275–352, at p.304.

⁷¹ Vignau (2013), p.191.

⁷² Fasi Kohler, *Mehrsimmiges [sic] Alphornblasen am Eidgen. Jodlerfest 1975 in Aarau*, Manuscript, Lucerne State Archive, PA 404/155, translation from the German by the authors.

⁷³ Hermann Graber, *Freiwillige Sitzung der Alphornbläser, Obmänner – Kampfrichter und Kursleiter der Unterverbände des E.J.V.*, Manuscript, Lucerne State Archive, PA 404/285.

In this comprehensive overview of the transformations of the Swiss alphorn, the evolution of the instrument over time can be observed. There is no linear continuity in the developments of length, form and modes of playing; instead, different features emerge at certain points in time and in specific regions. The model of today's alphorn, being more popular than ever, is the result of these multifaceted trials and innovations throughout history.

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